

Ultra Supermassive and Supermassive Black Holes of Intense Gravity are Even Lighter than Water or Gas

Dr. Goutam Sarker,
Associate Professor (Retired),
Computer Science and Engineering Department,
NIT Durgapur, INDIA

If all on a sudden I tell you all that there are a plenty of black holes, especially supermassive (hundreds of thousands to billions of times of solar mass) and ultra supermassive (more than 10 billion solar mass) black holes in this universe (and probably beyond this universe, i.e. I mean to say, the universe of universe) which are even lighter than water or even lighter than any gas – what would you think about me? I apprehend that few of you may even question my overall health. A black hole (irrespective of whether it is ultra supermassive, or supermassive or mini or primordial) is always with abnormally intense gravity – a gravity with which even light cannot escape out of it. So, all the information is trapped for ever, inside it. These are all well known buzzwords and lectures for any black hole, with which I am particularly very scared to disgust and bore you all. But how such an extreme abnormally intense gravitating body as well as huge ultra supermassive and supermassive body might have density too small? – Apparently quite unbelievable.

I was also little surprised like you, when I was making some other interesting calculations before my bedtime, early this week. The calculations were to relate critical radius of any black hole with its volume (which according to me, may be better justified to tell as 'critical volume').

We all know that the critical radius R_s of any black hole is related to its mass M by the universal relationship:

$$R_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2} \text{ --- (1)}$$

This implies that any mass M cannot be a black hole if its radius is more than R_s (critical radius).

So, the critical radius of any black hole is directly proportional to its mass M . Thus, the critical volume of any black hole (as for example specifically $v_s = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_s^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3$ for Schwarzschild black hole) is also directly proportional to the cube of its mass M .

So, equivalently, the mass M cannot be black hole if its volume is more than the critical volume v_s .

(a) So, any mass M to become a black hole should have the radius R_s which should satisfy the equation (1) above.

(b) Similarly for any mass M to become a (Schwarzschild) black hole, it should have the critical volume given by:

$$v_s = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_s^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3 \text{ --- (2)}$$

Thus, mass M cannot be a black hole in case its volume is more than v_s .

Now let us calculate the density of the black hole with the above critical volume. Density would be (I like to tell it critical density – keeping analogy with critical radius and critical volume)

$$d = ds = \frac{M}{\frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3} \quad \text{--- (3)}$$

So equivalently, the mass M cannot be a black hole if its density is less than the critical density ds

And from equation (3) for the black hole, the density is inversely proportional to the square of its mass.

It is justified to relate mass of any black hole with its volume or density instead of its radius. This is because of the fact that apart from Schwarzschild black holes (which are merely theoretical in our universe or others) all other black holes are not spherical. But they all should have a volume and density.

Anyway, from equation (3) it is clear that as the mass of the black hole increases, its density sharply decreases by a factor which is the square of the mass. The more massive the black hole is, the less dense it is.

Now you can guess what would happen to the density for all supermassive (hundreds of thousands to billions of times of solar mass) or ultra supermassive (more than 10 billion solar mass) black holes. Indeed, they are surprisingly too much lighter – even lighter than water or gas.